

High-performance p-type monolayer tungsten diselenide transistors

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Two-dimensional semiconductors are potential channel materials for future scaled complementary transistor technologies due to their high carrier mobility and strong immunity to the short-channel effect. However, electrical performance of p-type transistors is still far below that of their n-type counterparts. Here we report high-performance p-type monolayer tungsten diselenide (WSe₂) transistors with a hole mobility of 137 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ and a contact resistance of approximately 560 Ω·μm at room temperature. Our approach uses an industry-compatible and tunable oxygen-incorporated technique to heal defect states. Ultrascaled p-type monolayer WSe₂ transistor with a channel length of 45 nm exhibits an on-state current of 1245 μA/μm with an on/off ratio of ~10⁹, filling the large gap for p-type two-dimensional transistors.

Silicon complementary metal-oxide semiconductor (CMOS) technology will reach its performance limits at the sub 3 nm technology node¹. Two-dimensional (2D) semiconducting transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDs) are a potential replacement channel material for silicon due to their dangling-bond-free surfaces, high carrier mobility at the monolayer scale, and electrostatic control immunity from the short-channel effect^{2,3}. To achieve further scaling of CMOS technology with 2D semiconductor materials, both n- and p-type high-performance metal-oxide-semiconductor field-effect transistors (MOSFETs) are needed. Substantial progress has been made in 2D nFETs (using monolayer MoS₂, for example), but the performance of 2D pFETs is far from expected⁴⁻⁷.

Monolayer WSe₂ is a layered semiconductor with a direct bandgap of around 1.65 eV and a low effective mass ($0.44m_0$ for electrons and $0.41m_0$ for holes) that can also be grown over a large area by chemical vapor deposition (CVD)⁸⁻¹³. Despite its high intrinsic hole mobility, there is no reliable and practical method for fundamentally solving the hole mobility degradation problem of WSe₂ transistors because natural selenium vacancies (V_{Se}) can induce defect states and act as scatter centers to lower carrier mobility¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Accordingly, the contact resistance (R_c) between p-type monolayer WSe₂ and metals is typically in the range of 3-200 k Ω · μm due to the presence of high Schottky barriers, which greatly limits the output current of p-type WSe₂ transistors, especially in short-channel devices¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Therefore, industry-compatible approaches to passivate V_{Se} in WSe₂ films and improve the hole carrier mobility and lower the Schottky barrier height (SBH) and R_c for high-performance pFETs with a large drive current are needed.

In this Article, we report a tunable oxygen incorporation technique that can passivate V_{Se} in monolayer WSe₂ and improve the electrical performance of p-type monolayer WSe₂ transistors. The field-effect hole mobility (μ_{FE}) of monolayer oxygen-incorporated WSe₂ (O₂-WSe₂) is as high as 137 cm²V⁻¹ s⁻¹ at room temperature, approximately three times greater than that of pristine WSe₂. The p-type O₂-WSe₂ transistors achieve a low SBH of around 49 meV and a low contact resistance of around 560 Ω · μm due to suppression of the defect-induced states. The short channel 45-nm monolayer O₂-WSe₂ pFET exhibits a high on-state current (I_{on}) of 1245 $\mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$, which is higher than the performance in the nFET counterpart.

Monolayer WSe₂ nFETs and pFETs

Monolayer WSe₂ crystals were grown on sapphire and 100 nm SiO₂/Si substrates using low-pressure CVD in a 1-inch diameter quartz tube furnace (see Methods for details), and typical optical images are shown in Supplementary Fig. 1¹¹. For optical and electrical studies, monolayer WSe₂ films grown on sapphire were transferred onto 100 nm SiO₂/Si substrates using wet transfer approaches and monolayer WSe₂ films grown on SiO₂/Si substrates did not require a typical transfer process (Supplementary Fig. 2). The atomic force microscopy (AFM) and Raman results in Supplementary Fig. 3 confirm the presence of a monolayer and high-quality WSe₂ film⁸. Figure 1a,b shows the representative transfer and output characteristics of transferred monolayer WSe₂ FETs on 100-nm SiO₂ gate dielectrics at a 2 μm channel length (L_{ch}) with a Ni metal contact. The device shows n-type transistor behavior and a high on/off ratio of 10⁸. The field-effect electron mobility of monolayer WSe₂ was 5.8 cm² V⁻¹ s⁻¹ ($\mu_{\text{FE}} = g_{\text{m}}L/(WC_{\text{ox}}V_{\text{ds}})$, where g_{m} is the transconductance, W and L are the channel width and length, respectively, V_{ds} is the source-drain voltage and $C_{\text{ox}} = 0.034 \mu\text{F}/\text{cm}^{-2}$ is the gate capacitance). Notably, the electron mobility can be improved two-fold via the use of high k dielectrics (Supplementary Fig. 4) due to dielectric screening²⁰. Using epitaxial growth of high-quality films and semimetal contacts such as Bi or Sb, and soft metals such as In, the carrier mobility and electrical performance of monolayer WSe₂ nFETs are expected to further improved^{4,21,22}. In addition, when Ti and Pt metal contacts are deposited by the common method of e-beam evaporation, the monolayer WSe₂ transistor also exhibited consistent n-type transistor behavior due to Fermi-level

pinning (Supplementary Fig. 5). To prove the Fermi pinning position, we measured the temperature-dependent electrical properties to extract the Schottky barrier heights (SBHs) for transferred WSe₂ transistors with different contact materials (Supplementary Fig. 6). Both low and high work function metals are aligned near the conduction band of the transferred monolayer WSe₂, resulting in a monotonous n-type electrical characteristics (Fig. 1c). We also fabricated transistors based on monolayer WSe₂ directly grown on 100 nm SiO₂/Si substrates using a global gated structure with three kinds of contact metals, including the low-work-function metal Ti, and the high-work-function metals Ni and Pt. The transfer characteristics of monolayer WSe₂ FETs with Ti and Ni metal contacts exhibit ambipolar and p-type transistor behaviors, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 7). Figure 1d shows the transfer characteristics of monolayer WSe₂ FETs using Pt metal contacts, which also clearly exhibit p-type transistor behavior and a high on/off ratio of $\sim 10^8$. The field-effect hole mobility of monolayer WSe₂ was $45.2 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The corresponding output characteristics are shown in Fig. 1e. The 2- μm -long WSe₂ device has a drain current I_{ds} of $\sim 50 \mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$ at $V_{\text{ds}} = -2 \text{ V}$. The corresponding SBHs for the p-type WSe₂ transistors are shown in Supplementary Fig. 8. Figure 1f shows a scheme of the band diagram of the different work function pinning positions of the contact metals to monolayer WSe₂. Therefore, monolayer WSe₂ grown on sapphire and SiO₂/Si substrates shows opposite transport types. Using n- and p-type WSe₂, we demonstrated a WSe₂-based CMOS circuit-an inverter (Supplementary Fig. 9).

Gate-dependent PL measurements at 3.4 K

We perform low-temperature PL measurements to investigate the defect states in two types of monolayer WSe₂. The first type of material was originally grown on sapphire and then transferred to SiO₂/Si substrates (transferred WSe₂), and the other type of material was grown directly on SiO₂/Si substrates (as-grown WSe₂), as shown in Fig.2 (also shown in Supplementary Fig. 10). With decreasing temperature to 20 K, the resonance energies of free-excitons blueshift for both samples, which is in agreement with previous studies²³. Additionally, both samples exhibit a broad PL emission peak at lower energies, with the intensity increasing as the temperature decreases. This is attributed to the defect-bound excitons X_D²⁴. To gain a better understanding of the exciton states in WSe₂, we conducted gate-dependent PL measurements at 3.4 K. The PL spectra of both types of samples at different gate voltages (V_{gs}) are plotted in Fig. 2a,b (also shown in Supplementary Fig. 11). The PL emission of free-excitons at higher photon energies (ranging from 1.65 to 1.75 eV) can be deconvoluted by two Gaussian functions. These functions are assigned to charged and neutral A-excitons, respectively (X_A^- and X_A^0 in Fig. 2a, X_A^+ and X_A^0 in Fig. 2b). In the transferred WSe₂ samples, as V_{gs} increases from 0 V to 20 V (more electrons are doped into WSe₂), the X_A^- resonance energy moves to higher energy and its oscillator strength (plotted in Fig. 2c) diminishes as the X_A^0 resonance develops a redshift due to Coulomb screening, suggesting that these samples are initially n-doped. In contrast, the as-grown WSe₂ samples exhibit a similar trend for the X_A^0 and the X_A^+ resonances when V_{gs} decreases from 0 V to -20 V, indicating that these samples are p-doped at $V_{gs} = 0$. Similar behaviors have also been

observed in gated high-quality exfoliated samples^{25,26}. To further elucidate the nature of the bound excitons, we plot $I_B/(I_B + I_F)$ as a function of V_{gs} (Fig. 2d), where I_B and I_F are the accumulated PL intensities for bound excitons and free excitons, respectively. The intensities for both samples decrease with increasing carrier density, which is attributed to a Coulomb screening effect²⁷. In addition, the I_B of the transferred WSe₂ samples is greater than that of the as-grown WSe₂ samples, indicating a high defect state density. The gate-dependent peak energies of the B1 and B2 bound exciton emissions are shown in Fig. 2e. The resonance energies of the B2 bound excitons for both types of samples show weak gate-dependence, which is related to structural defects^{14,16,26}. The B1 peaks show the same trend when the carrier density increases, which can be attributed to the exciton recoil effects²⁶. Selenium vacancies (V_{se}) have been identified as the predominant point defects in CVD-grown monolayer WSe₂, independent of the substrate²⁸. These vacancies can be healed by means of oxygen passivation. In addition, V_{se} has been reported as the primary contributor to the n -type conductivity in unintentionally doped WSe₂, whereas the p -type conductivity in unintentionally doped WSe₂ is still under debate and has been attributed to tungsten vacancies (V_w) or to complex defects (O- V_w or O- V_{se}) with oxygen (given that oxygen is present in the growth conditions)²⁹⁻³³. We identified the B1 state in the transferred WSe₂ film as a V_{se} -induced donor-type bound exciton state, which experiences a blueshift in resonance energy when external electrons are introduced. In contrast, the B1 state in the directly grown WSe₂ film is an acceptor-type bound exciton state, whose origin can be attributed to the combined contribution from spotted V_w or to the

formation of complex O- V_W or O- V_{Se} defects, with its resonance energy also exhibiting a blueshift as external holes are introduced.

Improved performance of monolayer WSe₂ pFETs with oxygen passivation

To decrease the defect density in monolayer WSe₂, we developed an industry-compatible and tunable O₂ annealing process that tunes the performance of monolayer WSe₂ transistors by varying the O₂ flow to tune the vacuum level in the furnace before annealing. Figure 3a shows the low-temperature PL measurements of pristine WSe₂ and WSe₂ annealed in O₂ at 430 mTorr (O₂-WSe₂) (see Supplementary Fig. 12 for WSe₂ annealed at 26 mTorr (O-WSe₂)). The bound-exciton-associated accumulative PL intensities ($I_B/(I_B + I_F)$) for the pristine and O₂-WSe₂ samples are 0.95 and 0.65, respectively. Therefore, the significantly lower intensities of the B1 and B2 peaks for O₂-WSe₂ corroborate a lower defect density after O₂ annealing at 430 mTorr. Figure 3b, c shows the transfer and output characteristics of a 2- μ m-long O₂-WSe₂ pFET with an ultrahigh on/off of 10^{10} at a V_{ds} of -2 V. The μ_{FE} at room temperature is $137 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is three times larger than that of pristine WSe₂ (Supplementary Fig. 13). We also present the statistical distribution of the μ_{FE} (Fig. 3d) and the average μ_{FE} values of the pristine and O₂-WSe₂ pFETs are 40 and $122 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 14). The O₂ annealing process was also applied to the transferred monolayer WSe₂ transistor, which exhibited improved p-type transport capacity after O₂ annealing (Supplementary Fig. 15). Moreover, the drain current of monolayer WSe₂ decreases by ~ 2 times after annealing at 200 °C in Ar, indicating that oxygen plays an important

role in passivating V_{s_c} (Supplementary Fig. 16). High-angle annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) also revealed that selenium vacancies can be passivated by O_2 annealing (Supplementary Fig. 17)³⁴. We also did not observe the formation of WO_x in terms of Raman, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), or transmission electron microscopy (TEM) characterization (Supplementary Figs. 18 and 19). Higher temperature annealing causes the formation of WO_x and the degradation of drain current and subthreshold swing (Supplementary Fig. 20). Therefore, the higher hole mobility in O_2 -WSe₂ is mainly attributed to the effective passivation of the Se vacancies and the decrease in the defect density in the WSe₂ film by oxygen incorporation^{34,35}. The corresponding contact resistance R_c is extracted using the transmission line method (TLM) structure, and the results are shown in Fig. 3e. The extracted R_c of pristine WSe₂ is 2.4 k Ω · μ m, which can be reduced to 0.56 k Ω · μ m for the O_2 -WSe₂ pFET at a carrier density $n_s = 1.1 \times 10^{13}$ cm⁻². To investigate the Schottky barrier heights of monolayer WSe₂ devices, a thermionic emission model was applied to extract the Schottky barriers at the Pt/WSe₂ junction (Supplementary Fig. 21)³⁶. The SBH in the O_2 -WSe₂ FET under flat-band conditions is 49 meV, which is much lower than that extracted from pristine WSe₂ devices (155 meV). The decrease in the SBH caused by O_2 annealing was further confirmed by theoretical calculations (Supplementary Figs. 22-24). Figure 3f shows the SBH versus R_c for monolayer WSe₂ with and without O_2 annealing. As expected, O_2 -WSe₂ FETs exhibit a low R_c of approximately 0.56 k Ω μ m owing to their low SBH.

Theoretical analysis of monolayer WSe₂ with Se vacancies and oxygen passivation

To provide physical insights into the experimental results, we performed *ab-initio* Density Functional Theory (DFT) using the Quantum Espresso suite³⁷. Specifically, we focused on the effects of V_{Se} and oxygen (O and O₂) passivation of monolayer WSe₂. In Fig. 4 we report the relaxed crystal structure of all the studied geometries (Fig. 4a), the band structure, and the Projected Density of States (PDOS) for pristine WSe₂ (Fig. 4b), in the presence of a single selenium vacancy (Fig. 4c) and the case where the selenium vacancy is passivated with O (Fig. 4d) or O₂ (Fig. 4e) for a 4×4 WSe₂ supercell. We clearly observe that V_{Se}-WSe₂ produces a defective state that disappears when the vacancy is passivated with O or O₂, in agreement with the experimental findings described above. In addition, we observe from the PDOS that in the O-WSe₂ and O₂-WSe₂ structures, a state appears close to the top of the valence band, which is more pronounced in the O₂-WSe₂ structure, and can indicate p-type doping, as observed experimentally. We also note that the presence of oxygen, in addition to removing defects state close to the bottom of the conduction band, changes the band structure with respect to that of pristine WSe₂. This difference is more pronounced for O₂-WSe₂ but also for O-WSe₂ and can motivate the change in the transport properties observed in O-WSe₂ pFETs²⁷.

We also studied the impact of different V_{Se} concentrations to understand the different (n- or p-) types of behaviors observed experimentally. To do so, we considered V_{Se} concentrations of 4%, 6.3%, 12.5%, 18.8% and 25% obtained by including a single vacancy in a 5×5 (4%) and a 4×4 (6.3%) supercell and two (12.5%), three (18.8%) and

four vacancies (25%) in a 4×4 supercell (see Supplementary Fig. 25 for more details)³⁸. We performed two separate sets of calculations with and without spin-orbit coupling (SOC). In Fig. 4f we report the energy difference between the minimum unoccupied defect state and the Fermi energy level ($\Delta E = E_{defect\ state\ min} - E_F$) as defined in Fig. 4c. A smaller ΔE indicates a n-type behavior, whereas larger values indicate p-type behavior. In Fig. 4f we clearly observe that, as the density of defects increases, ΔE decreases, leading to a switch from p- (with no-defects or low-density Se vacancies) to n-type behavior, both in the case with and without SOC. We finally observe, as expected, a smaller value of ΔE for the case with SOC, due to the splitting of the defect state³⁹.

High-performance short-channel monolayer O₂-WSe₂ pFETs

To demonstrate the performance potential of monolayer O₂-WSe₂ transistors, channel length scaling was performed using 15 nm SiO₂ as the gate dielectric, as illustrated in the inset of Fig. 5a. Figure 5a shows the transfer characteristics of monolayer O₂-WSe₂ pFETs with L_{ch} values of 45 nm and 500 nm. Both devices exhibit high on/off ratios due to the atomically thin channel materials. Moreover, the 45-nm-long short-channel device has an excellent on/off ratio of nearly 10⁹ at $V_{ds} = -0.1$ V, indicating its promising application in low-power electronics. Moreover, O₂ annealing can also reduce the subthreshold swing and drain-induced barrier lowering (DIBL) of WSe₂ transistors (Supplementary Fig. 26), which can be further improved by decreasing the thickness of the gate dielectrics (Supplementary Fig. 27). In addition, a

shift in V_{th} (threshold voltage) toward a positive voltage for the 45-nm-long device was observed because of the contact-doping effect (Supplementary Fig. 28). Moreover, the device with O_2 annealing exhibited excellent stability (Supplementary Figs. 29,30). Figure 5b shows the corresponding output characteristics of the 500 nm short-channel transistor, which exhibited a high drain current of $823 \mu A/\mu m$ at $V_{gs} = -9$ V and $V_{ds} = -4$ V. With scaling down to 45 nm, the maximum I_{on} at $V_{gs} = -9$ V and $V_{ds} = -1.2$ V increased from $367 \mu A/\mu m$ to $1245 \mu A/\mu m$ (Fig. 5c) without the observation of a self-heating effect in high-field transport²¹, which is contrary to that of n-type MoS_2 . Figure 5d shows the benchmark μ_{FE} as a function of the on/off ratio in comparison with previous studies on p-type monolayer WSe_2 (see Supplementary Table 1 for details)^{13,18,23,40-46}. It is clear that the O_2 - WSe_2 transistor in this work concomitantly achieves both the highest μ_{FE} and on/off ratio, indicating promising applications for ultimate CMOS scaling with high-performance low-power electronic transistors. We also benchmarked our transistor performance with R_c , a key parameter limiting the scaling of I_{on} (Fig. 5e)^{17,19,40,47}. Compared with the other p-type doping methods, a low R_c of $\sim 560 \Omega \cdot \mu m$ is achieved through a standard CMOS-compatible annealing process, which promises good reliability and scalability. We compare the I_{on} in this work with other monolayer WSe_2 pFETs reported in the literature at the same $V_{ds} = -1$ V and maximum V_{gs} (Fig. 5f and Supplementary Fig. 31)^{17-19,21,23,40,41}. Due to the significant reduction in R_c , the present work showed the highest performance at various L_{ch} values compared with the values reported in the literature (Supplementary Table 1). Moreover, the I_{on} of monolayer WSe_2 pFETs is greater than that of p-type Si transistors at similar

technology node⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ and satisfies the 2028 roadmap target for high-performance logic transistors^{21,46}. The I_{on} of the monolayer WSe₂ pFET at an L_{ch} of 45 nm in this work is also higher than that of the best results for n-type monolayer MoS₂ in the literature²¹. These results indicate that oxygen doping by annealing under vacuum conditions is an effective and reliable way to realize high-performance WSe₂ pFETs with low R_c and high I_{on} .

Conclusions

We have reported an industry-compatible low-temperature oxygen-incorporated technology that can passivate selenide vacancies and suppress defect states in CVD monolayer WSe₂. The incorporation of oxygen not only increases the hole carrier mobility ($\sim 137 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$) and decreases the SBH and contact resistance. A drain current of $1245 \mu\text{A}/\mu\text{m}$ at a V_{ds} of -1.2 V is achieved in p-type monolayer WSe₂, which outperforms equivalent silicon CMOS technologies and satisfies the 2028 roadmap target. In addition to p-type WSe₂, we also demonstrated high-performance p-type molybdenum ditelluride (MoTe₂) devices (Supplementary Fig. 32), suggesting that low-temperature oxygen-incorporated technology may be a general doping technology for creating high-performance p-type transistors for CMOS applications.

Methods

Growth of monolayer WSe₂. WSe₂ single crystals were grown by a molten-salt-assisted low-pressure chemical vapor deposition (LPCVD) process. First, Se (Sigma-

Aldrich, $\geq 99.5\%$) was prepared in a ceramic boat, WO_2 (Alfa Aesar, 99.99%) and KCl (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.999%) were placed in a corundum boat with SiO_2/Si and sapphire substrates as described above. Then, the precursors were placed in a vacuum one-inch tube furnace. Finally, the crystals were grown at 890 °C for 10 minutes under low pressure (1700 Pa) with a mixture of 100 standard cubic centimeters per minute (sccm) Ar and 9 sccm H_2 as the carrier gas. After growth, the furnace was naturally cooled to room temperature.

Transfer of monolayer WSe_2 . After CVD growth, monolayer WSe_2 crystals on sapphire were transferred onto a target substrate using a wet transfer process. Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) was first spin-coated onto the as-grown $\text{WSe}_2/\text{sapphire}$ as a protection layer. Then a thermal release tape (TRT) was applied to the PMMA/ $\text{WSe}_2/\text{sapphire}$ to avoid possible folding during the transfer process. The TRT/PMMA/ $\text{WSe}_2/\text{sapphire}$ stacked film was immersed in deionized water for 4 hours. Next, the TRT/PMMA/ WSe_2 stacked film was placed on the target substrate; the TRT was released by baking on a hot-plate at 100 °C; and the PMMA film was finally removed by immersing the sample in acetone for 12 hours, leaving behind monolayer WSe_2 crystals on the target substrate.

Preparation of the STEM sample. The STEM samples were prepared with a wet-etching transfer method. The PMMA was spin-coated on a SiO_2/Si substrate deposited with monolayer WSe_2 flakes. The obtained substrate was then immersed in a KOH

solution (2 M) and DI water sequentially to etch the SiO₂ layers and remove the KOH residue. Afterward, a film floated on the water and was fished by a TEM grid to obtain a PMMA/WSe₂/Grid structure. After drying overnight in a nitrogen cabinet, the mentioned structure was dropped into acetone and then annealed (with or without O₂) at 250 °C under vacuum for 2 h to remove the PMMA.

TEM and STEM. Cross-sectional TEM lamellas of the FET samples were prepared using a Thermo Scientific Helios G4 HX dual-beam FIB/SEM machine using in-situ FIB lift-out technology. Before extraction and thinning, we coated the surface of the sample with a carbon film to protect the sample surface from ion beam damage. HAADF-STEM and cross-sectional TEM were performed using a Thermo Scientific Themis Z-aberration corrected transmission electron microscope or a Thermo Scientific Tecnai F20 at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. EDS mapping were obtained using the Super X FEI System in STEM mode. All the above characterization methods were performed by Eurofins EAG Materials Science China.

Material characterization. Monolayer WSe₂ was confirmed using Raman and photoluminescence spectra measurements at a laser wavelength of 532 nm. Raman spectroscopy was obtained through inVia Reflex manufactured by Renishaw. For temperature-dependent PL, a Montana Instruments Cryo Advance was used to control the temperature and a Keithley 2450 was used to provide the gate voltage. The test light path was homemade and all the PL spectra were acquired in vacuum environment. AFM

was carried out with an SPM-9700 in dynamic mode. SEM images were obtained with a Raith 150-Two. XPS was performed at the Huazhong University of Science and Technology Analytical & Testing Center using an AXIS SUPRA+.

Device Fabrication and Measurement. For back-gate device fabrication, both WSe₂ materials grown directly on SiO₂ and transferred from sapphire were patterned by electron beam lithography (EBL). AR-P 6200.13 e-beam resists are used during the plasma etching of WSe₂ films. Then, the channel was isolated by reactive-ion-etch (SHL 100 μ -RIE) with 100/10/80 sccm flow of Ar/O₂/CF₄ gas at 3 W for 180 s followed by immersing the sample in N-Methyl pyrrolidone (NMP) for 15 hours to remove the e-beam resist AR-P 6200.13. After annealing at 250 °C for 2 hours with 100 sccm Ar to remove AR-P residuals, S/D contacts were defined by EBL on the PMMA A4 resist and formed with metal deposition by E-beam evaporation. After the metal was lifted from unwanted regions with acetone, the p-type WSe₂ devices were annealed in an O₂ atmosphere under different vacuum conditions for 2 h at 200 °C. Electrical characteristic measurements were characterized at a Lakeshore probe station at room temperature under vacuum ($<10^{-5}$ Torr) using an Agilent B1500A semiconductor parameter analyzer.

Theoretical methods. Density functional theory (DFT) package in the Atomistix ToolKit (ATK) is used for the calculation of geometric optimization and band alignment properties⁵². The Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) approach under the generalized

gradient approximation (GGA) is employed to describe the exchange correlation interaction⁵³. The SG15 pseudopotential is used as the ultra-basis set with a density mesh cut-off of 90 Hartree. For geometric optimization, the convergence criteria of energy and force are 10^{-5} eV and 0.02 eV/Å, respectively. The Brillouin zone integrations are sampled with a $6\times 6\times 1$ k-point mesh. A vacuum layer of 40 Å is used to eliminate the interactions between periodic boundaries. For with spin-orbit coupling (SOC) calculations, we use SOGGA exchange-correlation interaction with SG15-SO pseudopotential. The DFT-D3 is employed for the analysis of vertical contact systems⁵⁴.

To study the effect of V_{sc} and oxygen (O and O_2) passivation of monolayer WSe_2 , density functional theory calculations have been performed with the Quantum-Espresso suite with and without spin-orbit coupling³⁴. We used projector augmented-wave pseudopotentials (PAW) within the Perdew-Burke-Ernzerhof (PBE) approximation for the exchange-correlation functional. All the structures considered were geometrically relaxed until all the forces were smaller than 0.051 eV/Å. For the electronic structure calculations, we considered an energy convergence threshold of 10^{-6} Ry, and an $8\times 8\times 1$ Gamma centered k-mesh grid.

Data availability:

The data that support the plots within this paper are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Author contributions:

G.F, X.L, and X.M. proposed and supervised the project. L.S and T.G. fabricated and measured the devices. T.C., D.M. G.I., G.F., J.Y., and S.Z., performed and discussed the first-principles calculations. L.S, X.L., and T.G. performed the XPS, SEM, AFM, PL, and Raman characterizations. All authors discussed the results and wrote the paper. L.S. and T.G. contributed equally to this work.

Competing financial interests:

The authors declare no competing financial interests.

Additional information

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Fig. 1 | Monolayer WSe₂ nFETs and pFETs. Transfer (a) and output (b) characteristics of monolayer WSe₂ FETs with Ni metal contact at $V_{ds} = 0.1$ and 1 V. Monolayer WSe₂ is grown on sapphire substrates and then transferred to 100 nm SiO₂/Si substrates. The insets in (a) and (d) show optical images of monolayer WSe₂ crystals grown on sapphire and SiO₂/Si substrates by CVD, respectively. The scale bar is 10 μm . c,f Schematic band diagram showing the different workfunction pinning positions of the contact metals to the monolayer WSe₂ transferred from the sapphire substrates as well as the monolayer WSe₂ directly grown on SiO₂/Si. ϕ_m : work function of a metal. ϕ_{CNL} : charge neutrality level. d, Transfer characteristics of monolayer WSe₂ FETs directly grown on SiO₂/Si substrates. e, Corresponding output characteristics of the monolayer WSe₂ FETs in (d).

Fig. 2 | Gate-dependent PL of monolayer WSe₂ at 3.4 K. **a,b**, PL spectra of WSe₂ transferred from sapphire (**a**) and WSe₂ directly grown on SiO₂/Si (**b**) at 3.4 K with different gate voltages (V_{gs}). Each spectrum is fitted with four Gaussian peaks, denoted as B1, B2, X_A, and X_A⁺ (or X_A⁺). **c**, Trion and exciton peak intensity versus gate voltage. **d**, Percentage of bound-exciton-associated accumulative PL intensity ($I_B/(I_B+I_F)$) as a function of V_{gs} . **e**, Peak positions E_{B1} and E_{B2} as a function of V_{gs} . **f**, Schematic illustration representing different origins of bound excitons in the two samples.

Fig. 3 | PL and electrical characterization of monolayer WSe₂ on SiO₂ before and after O₂ annealing. **a**, PL spectra of monolayer WSe₂ grown on SiO₂ substrates with and without O₂ annealing at 3.4 K. The fitted peaks can be assigned to neutral excitons (X_A), trions (X_A⁺), and defect-bound excitons (B1 and B2). Transfer (**b**) and output (**c**) characteristics of monolayer WSe₂ devices annealed in O₂ at 430 mTorr. The gate dielectric is 100 nm SiO₂. The channel length and width are 2 and 1 μm, respectively. The inset shows an SEM image of a WSe₂ TLM structure with a minimum L_{ch} of 100 nm. The scale bar is 2 μm. **d**, Distribution of the hole field-effect mobility (μ_{FE}) of monolayer WSe₂ before and after O₂ annealing at 430 mTorr. In the box plot, the box represents the interquartile range (IQR) from the 25th to the 75th percentile, and the line inside the box denotes the median. The whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum values, excluding outliers. For pristine WSe₂, n was 25. The minima, maxima, and center values are 29, 51, and 40, respectively. For O₂-WSe₂, n was 22. The minima, maxima, and center values are 93, 137, and 122, respectively. TLM resistances (**e**) of

monolayer WSe₂ pFETs before and after O₂ annealing at 430 mTorr. After annealing, R_c is determined to be 0.56 k Ω · μm at $n_s \sim 1.1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-2}$, which is four times lower than that of the pristine device. The channel lengths are 200 nm, 500nm, 1 μm , and 2 μm . **f**, R_c versus SBH. The R_c values are extracted from **(e)**.

Fig. 4 | First-principle theoretical simulations of pristine monolayer WSe₂, with V_{Se}, O- and O₂ passivation. a, Crystal structure of a 4×4 supercell of pristine WSe₂ (top left), with a single Se vacancy (top right), an O-passivated vacancy (bottom left) and an O₂-passivated vacancy (bottom right). **b-d**, Band structure and projected density of states (PDOS) without SOC for **(b)** pristine, **(c)** single selenium vacancy (including the definition of the energy difference between the minimum unoccupied defect state and the Fermi energy level (ΔE) as used in the main text), single selenium vacancy passivated with O **(d)** and O₂ **(e)**. **f**, ΔE as a function of the selenium vacancy concentration with and without SOC.

Fig. 5 | Device characterization of short-channel monolayer WSe₂ pFETs. **a**, Transfer characteristics of WSe₂ devices with channel lengths of 45 nm and 500 nm at 300 K. Inset: Schematic illustration of a monolayer WSe₂ device annealed with O₂ at 430 mTorr in this work. **b**, The corresponding output characteristics of WSe₂ pFETs in **(a)** with an L_{ch} of 500 nm. V_{gs} ranges from 2 to -9 V with steps of -1 V. **c**, Output characteristics of WSe₂ pFETs in **(a)** with an L_{ch} of 45 nm. V_{gs} ranges from 9 to -9 V with steps of -2 V. The inset shows an SEM image of a WSe₂ transistor with an L_{ch} of 45 nm. The scale bar is 100 nm. **d**, Summary of the on/off ratio and hole mobility for CVD monolayer WSe₂ transistors reported in the literature. The requirements of IRDS 2021 and other typical p-type TMD materials (WS₂ and MoTe₂) have also been added for comparison. Benchmark of the contact resistance R_c **(e)** and on-state current I_{on} **(f)** for CVD monolayer p-type WSe₂ transistors at room temperature. The black line in **(e)** represents the quantum limit of R_c . The reported highest I_{on} for monolayer MoS₂ nFETs (dark green with open symbols) at $L_{ch} = 40$ nm with $V_{ds} = 1$ V and p-type silicon

technology (deep yellow with half-filled symbols) have also been added for comparison.

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